

Some Properties of Resin Concrete Exposed to the Action of Fatigue Loading

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ABSTRACT

Addition of steel fibres into the resin concrete profitably changes a number of its properties e.g. increases its tensile and compressive strength, impact resistance as well as changes the character of material destruction.

On the base of the results of investigations carried out for the cement concrete with fibres addition it could be supposed that also for the resin concrete this addition will have a profitably effect on fatigue resistance increasing.

The range of carried out investigations was as follows:

- to determine of stable fatigue strength of resin concrete with and without the steel fibres addition
- to study of decrease of static strength of the material after the fatigue loading cycle
- to determine the effect of sample shape superficial module on the increase of the sample temperature during the fatigue loading.

The beneficial results of the investigations allows to appoint a widest range of application of resin concrete.

INTRODUCTION

Resin concretes thanks to such excellent qualities as high strength and rapid hardening are widely applicable in the industrial, municipal and housing structures. As the plain cement concretes the resin concretes have the agglomerate macrostructure but their shows different, specific properties. This is caused by the fact that in resin concretes a high - molecular substance polymer is used as a binder.

In particular cases of application of resin concretes for instance at increased temperatures their properties are changing disadvantageously and therefore the experimental checking is necessary.

During the fatigue loading the element temperature increasing caused by internal friction of texture particles which is particularly strong near the propagating defects and external

friction at the place of application of force is observed. In connection with the above an investigations which would allow to estimate the influence of heating of samples which are exposed to the action of fatigue loading on their fatigue and static strength were undertaken.

The fact that stresses and deformations of any point of section which are safe when appears singly could become destructive with multiple repetition determines particular significance of fatigue phenomenon. This phenomenon was already described in details for many basic materials (1).

In the case of plain cement concrete an advantageous influence of steel fibre addition on the concrete stable and restrained fatigue strength was also stated (2).

The phenomena described above have become the cause for undertaking of an fatigue investigations of resin concrete. An attempts were also undertaken with the aim of improvement of resin concrete properties by addition of steel fibres.

It should be also underlined that in other research centres the additives other than steel fibres were also used (3).

In the experiments the polyester resin "Polimal 108" with the following properties was used:

- specific gravity at 25°C, g/cm³ 1,05
- viscosity at 25°C 90 - 150
- gelation time at 20°C, min 20 - 45
- monomer content, % 44

Specimens were produced at the temperature 20°C and demoulded after 24 hours of curing. They were tested after 14 days of hardening at the temperature 20°C.

Mix proportions of resin concretes (in percent by weight) used in the experiments was as follows:

Concrete type A		Concrete type B	
sand 0/2 mm	80 %	sand 0/2 mm	44 %
resin "Polimal 108"	19,2 %	granite 2/5 mm	36 %
hardening complex	0,8 %	resin "Polimal 108"	19,2 %
		hardening complex	0,8 %

Addition of steel fibres 0,25/25 mm - 2 % by volume
The basic properties of concretes investigated at the temperature 20°C are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Basic properties of investigated resin concretes

Type of concrete	Flexural strength MPa	Compressive strength MPa	Tensile strength MPa	Modulus of elasticity under tension MPa	Modulus of elasticity under compression MPa
Resin concrete Polimal 108	18,7	65,9	6,07	16,8 · 10 ³	21,6 · 10 ³
Resin concrete with steel fibres	22,0	72,0	5,82	14,4 · 10 ³	19,5 · 10 ³

In this paper the results of first stage of an investigations are described. These investigations include:

- estimation of the effect of elements shape on their strength at the increased temperature,

- investigation of effect of fatigue loading on the sample temperature increasing,
- estimation of effect of temperature on the resin concrete static flexural and compressive strength,
- fatigue strength of investigated concretes,
- effect of fatigue of resin concrete on their static strength,
- effect of type of aggregate and addition of steel fibres on the mentioned properties of resin concrete.

TEST RESULTS

Effect of resin concrete temperature on their static strength

Effect of resin concrete temperature on their static strength was tested on the samples which were previously 8 hours heated to the temperature 40°C, 60°C and 80°C respectively. The results were compared to these obtained for samples tested at the temperature of 20°C. Two kinds of prisms 40x40x80 mm and 40x40x50 mm were used in the compressive tests while in the flexural tests specimens were prisms 40x40x160 mm.

In Table 2 and on Fig.1. the average value of six results for each type of concrete and temperature level are presented.

Table 2. Effect of temperature on static strength of resin concrete

Temp. °C	Compressive strength MPa								Flexural strength MPa			
	samples 40x40x80 mm				samples 40x40x50 mm				samples 40x40x160 mm			
	A	A+f	B	B+f	A	A+f	B	B+f	A	A+f	B	B+f
20	74,5	80,2	79,2	78,5	84,3	71,9	83,1	77,0	22,5	28,1	20,2	20,7
40	62,8	54,4	50,8	60,3	66,3	63,6	57,4	63,9	21,2	23,2	19,7	20,6
60	44,4	33,0	43,0	31,5	54,9	54,9	51,6	47,0	12,4	17,0	14,4	8,2
80	8,8	15,4	15,9	14,3	28,2	28,2	28,0	22,8	4,9	7,1	8,5	3,4

Symbols used in the tables and on figures:

- A - resin concrete based upon sand up to 2 mm
- A+f - resin concrete based upon sand up to 2 mm with the addition of steel fibres 2 % by volume
- B - resin concrete based upon granite aggregate up to 5 mm
- B+f - resin concrete based upon granite aggregate up to 5 mm with the addition of steel fibres 2 % by volume

Fig. 1. Effect of temperature of resin concrete on their compressive and flexural strength

The temperature of samples getting worm during the fatigue loading

The temperature of samples getting worm during the fatigue loading was measured on the samples surfans with the temperature-sensitive resistor while for measurements of temperature inside the samples a thermo-couples were used. It allows of statement that temperature inside the sample as soon as sample is fatigue destroyed was 5°C higher.

The following parameters of fatigue loading were chosen: $\rho = \sigma_{\min} / \sigma_{\max} = 0$, frequency $n = 600$ cycles per minute, variable maximum stress in cycle σ_{\max} from 0,6 till 0,4 of $\sigma_{\text{stress destructive}}$ at the temperature of 20°C.

The measurements of temperature were carried out after each 1000 cycles of fatigue loading and the results are shown in Table 3.

On Fig. 2 the results of fatigue strength are presented.

Table 3. Temperature of samples exposed to the action of fatigue loading

Amount of cycles	Temperature of samples surface °C					
	concrete without fibres - B			concrete with fibre addition B+f		
	$\sigma_{\max} = 0,6 R_C$	$\sigma_{\max} = 0,5 R_C$	$\sigma_{\max} = 0,4 R_C$	$\sigma_{\max} = 0,6 R_C$	$\sigma_{\max} = 0,5 R_C$	$\sigma_{\max} = 0,4 R_C$
0	23	23	23	23	23	23
1000	24	24	24	24	26	25
2000	27	25	25	26	29	28
3000	30	25	26	30	32	31
4000	35	27	27	38	39	37
5000	40	29	28	40	42	39
6000	-	33	32	42	43	42
7000	-	36	35	-	43	43
8000	-	38	37	-	44	44
9000	-	-	39	-	44	45
10000	-	-	40	-	45	46
	-	-	42	-	46	46

In table an average results for 5 samples 40x40x80 mm are presented.

Fig. 2. Fatigue strength of resin concrete

Static compressive strength of samples exposed to the action of fatigue loading

The tests of static compressive strength of samples 40x40x80 mm exposed to the action of fatigue loading were carried out immediately after finishing of definite number of fatigue loading cycles.

As variable parameter the amount of loading cycles was chosen. The parameter of cycle was chosen as in the investigation of fatigue strength i.e. $Q = 0$. Additionally the samples temperature during the fatigue loading was checked. The results obtained are presented in Table 4 and on Fig. 3.

Table 4. Static compressive strength of samples 40x40x80 mm exposed to the action of fatigue loading for $G_{max} = 0,4 R_C$

Number of cycles N	Type of concrete			
	B (without fibres)		B + f (with fibres)	
	Decrease of static strength after N-cycles %	Maximum temp. after N-cycles °C	Decrease of static strength after N-cycles %	Maximum temp. after N-cycles °C
5000	5,4	27	4,7	28
10000	11,7	36	5,5	38
100000	-	-	11,5	40

Fig. 3. Decrease of static compressive strength after N-cycles of fatigue loading for $\sigma_{\max} = 0,4 R_c$

DISCUSSION

The effect of temperature on strength of investigated resin concretes is very strong. Although concrete with granite aggregate up to 5 mm shows greater decrease of strength than the concrete with sand up to supposed that this is caused by quantity and proportions of internal structure defects which at the increased temperature are more visible for concretes with coarse aggregate.

The advantageous effect of steel fibres addition is observed only when they have a good adherence to the matrix i.e. to the temperature of 40°C. For 40x40x80 mm prisms compressed in vertical position a visibly greater than for 40x40x50 mm cubes decrease of concrete strength at increased temperature was observed.

Columnar shape of the element causes that the effect of disturbance at the set planes on the tensile stress diagram is smaller.

In connection with the above the effect of steel fibres addition is also manifested strongly in the columnar elements but only to the temperature of 50°C.

During the fatigue loading the worming of samples is the quicker the greater value of ζ . The final measured just before the failure temperatures of samples surfaces and interior were similar and reached the values 40-45°C and 45-50°C respectively. The samples which survived 2×10^6 cycles have reached temperature by about 5°C lower. Surfaces of samples with the addition of steel fibres reached slightly higher temperature by about 3 - 5°C but they carried greater amount of cycles of fatigue loading.

The samples static compressive strength decreases significantly many times more than for cement concretes as a result of sample exposing to the action of N cycles of fatigue loading. The advantageous effect of steel fibres addition is very clear as it reduces drop in strength particularly for great amount of fatigue loading cycles. This phenomenon is connected with increase in samples temperature.

CONCLUSIONS

Pretty large decrease of resin concrete strength at increased temperature as well as the fact of worming of the elements exposed

to the action of fatigue loading limits the possibilities of application of such kind of material when substantial frequency of loading change above 200 cycles per minute and high parameters of loading ($\xi > 0,4$) are used.

Advantageous shape of elements by affording possibilities for out si de heat abstraction slightly improves the strength of element. In large elements the local loss of material strength will determine its durability.

Under the fatigue loading the effect of steel fibres addition is explicitly advantageous since temperature of samples doesn't exceed the temperature of 50°C.

The decrease of static strength for samples exposed to the action of fatigue loading is considerable many times exceeds the values for cement concretes .

The effect of steel fibre addition is very advantageous.

Investigations of resin concrete fatigue strength should be carried out also with reference to the static strength tested at the temperature which is reached by the samples exposed to the action of fatigue loading.

REFERENCES

- 1 Korczyński, J.B., Procznost stroitielnykh Materialow pri dinamiczeskikh nagruženijach, Moscov, 1966
- 2 Sasiadek, S., Several Properties of Steel Fibre Reinforced Concrete (SFRC) Subject the Fatigue loading, III International Conference of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Varna 1982, Bulgaria
- 3 Kobayashi, K., Ito, T., Several physical properties of resin concrete, The concrete Society, The Construction Press Proceedings of the First International Congress, London, 1975

